
Federated Unlearning: How to Efficiently Erase a Client in FL?

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Abstract

With privacy legislation empowering users with the right to be forgotten, it has become essential to make a model forget about some of its training data. We explore the problem of removing any client’s contribution in federated learning (FL). During FL rounds, each client performs local training to learn a model that minimizes the empirical loss on their private data. We propose to perform unlearning at the client (to be erased) by reversing the learning process, i.e., training a model to *maximize* the local empirical loss. In particular, we formulate the unlearning problem as a constrained maximization problem by restricting to an ℓ_2 -norm ball around a suitably chosen reference model to help retain some knowledge learnt from the other clients’ data. This allows the client to use projected gradient descent to perform unlearning. The method does neither requires global access to the data used for training nor the history of the parameter updates to be stored by the aggregator (server) or any of the clients. Experiments on the MNIST dataset show that the proposed unlearning method is efficient and effective.

1. Introduction

Recent privacy legislation (Voigt & Von dem Bussche, 2017; Pardau, 2018; Act, 2000) provide to data owners the right to be forgotten. In the machine learning context, the right to be forgotten requires that (i) the user data is deleted from the entity storing it and (ii) the influence of the data on the model is removed. In this paper, we focus on machine unlearning in the context of federated learning. Federated learning (FL) is a recent approach which allows a set of distributed clients to jointly train a shared model while keeping their data on-premise (Kairouz et al., 2021). Even though the

clients do not exchange data with each-other or with the aggregator, there still exist some privacy risks (Nasr et al., 2019; Melis et al., 2019). Thus, it is necessary to develop efficient techniques that unlearn data sample(s) from the trained FL model.

Existing works on machine unlearning (Graves et al., 2020; Bourtole et al., 2021; Sekhari et al., 2021) can not be directly applied in a federated learning setting due to two main reasons: (i) FL uses an iterative process where all the participating clients contribute to learn the final model and (ii) the aggregator (server) does not have access to the training data possessed by the clients. The most naive way of implementing federated unlearning is to retrain the model from scratch after removing from the corresponding client(s) the data sample(s) that are requested to be deleted. However, this approach is computationally expensive. A few works (Liu et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2022) aiming to speed up this process have been proposed recently, but they either are not practical to be used in real-life (Liu et al., 2021) or require the server to store the history of the parameter updates (Wu et al., 2022). With many agents present in FL, each with different access rights, it isn’t immediately obvious who will conduct unlearning. In cases when a client performs a local unlearning step, broadcasting the update across the federation may exacerbate privacy risks of the erased client (Chen et al., 2021). Moreover, local unlearning may be inadequate as other checkpoints in the federation may still retain the memory of erased data. Therefore, unlearning user data in FL still remains an open problem.

In this paper, we consider the case where a client (referred to as the target client) wants to opt out of federation after the federated learning process, and as a result wants to remove their contribution from the global model. As an example, consider an FL scenario wherein multiple hospitals from different countries (or geographical regions) collaborate on training a model for tumor detection. After training the model, suppose one of the hospitals decides to opt out of federation due to changes in the privacy regulations in their country. Then, the question is how to unlearn the hospital’s data from the trained model. We argue that the hospital that wants to opt out can effectively perform unlearning by *reversing* the learning process.

In an FL training round, each client essentially solves an

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empirical risk minimization problem, and strives to learn a model that minimizes the empirical loss. We propose to perform unlearning at the target client (to be erased) by training a model to *maximize* the empirical loss. Instead of optimizing arbitrarily over the entire space of model parameters, we formulate the unlearning problem as a constrained maximization problem by restricting to an ℓ_2 -norm ball around a suitably chosen *reference model*. We argue that the average of the other clients’ local models (except the local model of the target client) in the last round of FL training is an effective reference model, as it helps to retain some knowledge learnt from the other clients’ data. This formulation allows the client to perform the unlearning by using the Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) algorithm. To improve the performance of the unlearned model, we continue the FL process for a few rounds without the participation of the target client. Our results on the MNIST dataset show that the proposed method successfully unlearns the contribution of the target client in an efficient way. In fact, our results demonstrate that just one round of FL process after unlearning is sufficient to yield the performance comparable to retraining from scratch for a large number of rounds.

2. Related Work

Machine Unlearning. The concept of machine unlearning, i.e., removing the impact of a data sample to the trained model, was first introduced by Cao & Yang (2015). After that, several algorithms for machine unlearning have been proposed, see, e.g., Du et al. (2019); Ginart et al. (2019); Guo et al. (2019); Baumhauer et al. (2020); Golatkar et al. (2020a,b); Graves et al. (2020); Bourtole et al. (2021); Neel et al. (2021); Sekhari et al. (2021); Thudi et al. (2021).

Federated Unlearning. Unlearning in the federated setup has received relatively less attention unlike the centralized setup. FedEraser (Liu et al., 2021) reconstructs the unlearned global model by adjusting the historical parameter updates of the participating clients. Even though FedEraser speeds up the unlearning process in comparison to retraining from scratch, it is still prohibitively expensive. Recently, Wu et al. (2022) developed an unlearning method which consists of erasing the historical parameter updates from the target client and recovering the model performance through the knowledge distillation process. Both these methods require the server to keep the history of the parameter updates from all the clients. Moreover, the knowledge-distillation approach requires the server to possess some extra outsourced unlabeled data. Satisfying these requirements may not be feasible in several application scenarios, especially with strict privacy regulations. In contrast, our proposed method relies on the target client (i.e., the client that wants to opt out of federation) and it does not require to store the parameter updates of the clients. Different from these works (and the

one we propose), Wang et al. (2022) proposed an unlearning framework to forget a particular category or class.

Backdoor Attacks and Unlearning. Backdoor attacks (Gu et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020) have raised several security concerns about training with third-party resources. They cause the trained model to conduct specific behaviours as the backdoor pattern is triggered. Trigger patterns vary from one single pixel (Gu et al., 2017) to human imperceptible noises (Li et al., 2020). Recently, Liu et al. (2022) proposed BaEraser, which erases the backdoor injected into the model via a gradient ascent machine unlearning method. However, they consider a centralized setting and require an access to clean samples during unlearning the backdoor trigger.

3. Background on Federated Learning

In a federated learning framework (McMahan et al., 2017), a (global) model is trained in a distributed way with the help of an aggregator, where each participating client contributes to training without sharing its data with the other participants. We consider the supervised federated learning setup with N clients, each with dataset $D_i = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i)_{i \in [n_i]}\}$ (where $[n_i] = \{1, 2, \dots, n_i\}$). The goal is to learn a model parameterized by weights $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. This is typically formulated as an empirical risk minimization problem: $\min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d} F(\mathbf{w}) := \sum_{i=1}^N p_i F_i(\mathbf{w})$, where $F_i(\cdot)$ is the local objective function at client i and p_i is the aggregation weight for client i . The local objective is $F_i(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j \in D_i} L(\mathbf{w}; (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j))$, where $L(\mathbf{w}; (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j))$ is the loss of the prediction on example (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j) made with model parameters \mathbf{w} . One of the popular loss functions for a classification task is the cross-entropy loss.

Federated learning systems typically use Federated Averaging (FedAvg) (McMahan et al., 2017) for training. In round t , the aggregator sends the current global model \mathbf{w}^t to the clients. Each client takes multiple steps of mini-batch stochastic gradient descent (SGD) with a fixed learning rate to update their local model, and sends their updated local model \mathbf{w}_i^t to the aggregator. Finally, the aggregator computes a weighted average of the local models to obtain the global model for the next round: $\mathbf{w}^{t+1} = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i \mathbf{w}_i^t$, where $p_i = \frac{n_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N n_i}$. The iterative training process is repeated for a specific T number of rounds.

We focus on the so-called *enterprise* or *cross-silo* setting in which clients are different organizations (e.g., banks or hospitals) (Kairouz et al., 2021). In this setting, the number of clients is often smaller, all the clients participate in each round, and every client possesses substantially large amount of data.

4. Federated Unlearning: Erasing a Client

4.1. Setup

In this work, we consider the following unlearning scenario in the FL setting. After FL training is performed with N clients for the specified T rounds, then a client $i \in [N]$ requests to opt out of federation and wants to remove their contribution from the FL model. We refer to this client as the *target client*. Similar to the centralized machine unlearning, the most legitimate way of erasing a client is to retrain the FL model from the beginning. However, retraining from scratch is often prohibitively expensive. Thus, in this work, we focus on approximate unlearning with the goal of obtaining a performance *close to* retraining.

4.2. Unlearning Metrics

Unlearning can be formally defined by considering the distribution of all models that a federated learning algorithm can produce and requiring that the distributions of retrained and unlearned models are *close* in some distance metric, similar to (Bourtoule et al., 2021). However, since computing a distance between distributions is typically expensive, prior works measure the quality of unlearning in terms of distance in the weight or output space of retrained and unlearned models, e.g., ℓ_2 -distance (Wu et al., 2020) or Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence (Golatkar et al., 2020a). Other metrics include privacy leakage in the differential privacy framework (Sekhari et al., 2021) and membership inference attacks (Graves et al., 2020; Baumhauer et al., 2020). In this paper, we follow the approach similar to Wu et al. (2022) described in the following.

Backdoors to Evaluate Unlearning: We use the backdoor triggers (Gu et al., 2017) as an effective way to evaluate the performance of unlearning methods, similar to Wu et al. (2022). In particular, the target client uses a dataset with a certain fraction of images which have a backdoor trigger inserted in them. Thus, the global FL model becomes susceptible to the backdoor trigger. Then, a successful unlearning process should produce a model that reduces the accuracy on the images with the backdoor trigger, while maintaining a good performance on regular (clean) images. Note that we use the backdoor triggers as a way to evaluate the performance of unlearning methods; we do not consider any malicious client nor apply any scaling/model replacement as in Bagdasaryan et al. (2020). As a future work, we will explore other metrics such as the accuracy of the membership inference attacks (Nasr et al., 2019) on the unlearned data of the target client, ℓ_2 -distance between a model retrained from a naive approach and the one obtained via the proposed approach (described in the next section).

5. Unlearning with Projected Gradient Ascent

During a federated training round t , the goal of a client is to learn a local model that *minimizes* the (local) empirical risk, i.e., to solve the following optimization problem:

$$\text{(Train)} \quad \min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d} F_i(\mathbf{w}) := \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j \in D_i} L(\mathbf{w}; (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j)), \quad (1)$$

where $L(\mathbf{w}; (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j))$ is the loss of the prediction on example (\mathbf{x}_j, y_j) made with model parameters \mathbf{w} . Each client locally makes several passes of (mini-batch stochastic) *gradient descent* to find a model that has *low* empirical loss. (It is also possible to use other optimization algorithms.)

We argue that a natural idea for unlearning is to *reverse* this learning process. That is, during unlearning, instead of learning model parameters that minimize the empirical loss, the client strives to learn the model parameters to *maximize* the loss. To find a model with *large* empirical loss, the client can simply make several local passes of (mini-batch stochastic) *gradient ascent*. However, simply maximizing the loss with gradient ascent can be problematic, the loss is unbounded, which is often the case in practice, e.g., the cross-entropy loss. In the case of an unbounded loss, each gradient step moves towards a model that increases the loss, and after several steps it is likely to produce an arbitrary model similar to a random model.

To tackle this issue, we ensure that the unlearned model is *sufficiently close* to a *reference model* that has effectively learned the other clients' data distributions. In particular, we propose to use the average of the other clients' models as a reference model, i.e., $\mathbf{w}_{\text{ref}} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbf{w}_j^{T-1}$. Note that the target client i can compute this reference model locally as $\mathbf{w}_{\text{ref}} = \frac{1}{N-1} (N\mathbf{w}^T - \mathbf{w}_i^{T-1})$. The client i then optimizes over the model parameters that lie in the ℓ_2 -norm ball of radius δ around \mathbf{w}_{ref} . (The radius δ will be treated as a hyperparameter in our experiments.) Thus, during unlearning, the client solves the following optimization problem:

$$\text{(Unlearn)} \quad \max_{\mathbf{w} \in \{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}_{\text{ref}}\|_2 \leq \delta\}} F_i(\mathbf{w}), \quad (2)$$

where $F_i(\cdot)$ is defined in eq. (1).

An obvious choice for solving (2) is to use projected gradient ascent. More specifically, let us denote the ℓ_2 -norm ball of radius δ around \mathbf{w}_{ref} as $\Omega = \{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}_{\text{ref}}\|_2 \leq \delta\}$. Let $\mathcal{P} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the projector operator onto Ω . Then, for a given step-size η_u , client i iterates the update:

$$\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{w} + \eta_u \nabla F_i(\mathbf{w})). \quad (3)$$

To avoid learning an arbitrary model, we perform early stopping if the validation accuracy drops below a predetermined threshold τ (which is treated as a hyperparameter). Algorithm 1 describes the unlearning procedure, and a schematic is included in the appendix.

Algorithm 1 Unlearning via Projected Gradient Ascent

Unlearning Parameters: learning rate η_u , batch size B_u , number of epochs E_u , clipping radius δ , and early stopping threshold τ
 Split dataset D_i into train set D_i^{tr} and validation set D_i^{val}
 Set $\mathbf{w}_{ref} \leftarrow \frac{1}{N-1} (N\mathbf{w}^T - \mathbf{w}_i^{T-1}) = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbf{w}_j^{T-1}$
 Define $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{w})$ as the projection of $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ onto the ℓ_2 -norm ball $\Omega = \{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}_{ref}\| \leq \delta\}$
 Initialize unlearning model as $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_i^{T-1}$
 $D_i \leftarrow$ (split D_i^{tr} into batches of size B_u)
for each local epoch $e = 1$ **to** E_u **do**
 for batch b in D_i **do**
 $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{w} + \eta_u \nabla F_i^u(w; b))$
 if Accuracy($\mathbf{w}; D^{val}$) $< \tau$ **then**
 Set $\mathbf{w}_i^u \leftarrow \mathbf{w}$ and return \mathbf{w}_i^u to server
 end if
 end for
end for
 Set $\mathbf{w}_i^u \leftarrow \mathbf{w}$ and return \mathbf{w}_i^u to server

After client i performs unlearning, it is possible that the resulting model has a poor performance on the other clients’ data distribution. To remedy this, we propose to *improve* the unlearned model by performing a few rounds of FL training. In particular, the server starts with the unlearned model \mathbf{w}_i^u , and performs a few rounds of FL training (without the participation of the target client i). Interestingly, we demonstrate empirically in Sec. 6 that performing *just one round* of FL post-training on the unlearned model \mathbf{w}_i^u is sufficient in practice.

6. Evaluation

Dataset and Model Architecture: Our initial study is conducted on MNIST digit recognition task (Lecun et al., 1998) using a CNN from McMahan et al. (2017) with two 5×5 convolution layers, a fully connected layer with 512 units and ReLU activation, and a final softmax output layer (1,663,370 total parameters). We equally partition the 60000 training images across N clients in the FL process, one of which is the target client (i.e., the one that wants to opt out of federation). We detail out the hyperparameters used for FL training and unlearning in the appendix.

Evaluation Metric: As mentioned in Section 4.2, we use backdoor triggers to evaluate the performance of unlearning methods, similar to Wu et al. (2022). We use the accuracy metric on the clean data and on the backdoored data to measure the performance of the proposed unlearning method. We compute the accuracy on the backdoored data (referred as the backdoor accuracy) as the percentage of triggered (poisoned) data that are misclassified as the target label required by the attacker. Recall that we use the backdoor

attacks as a way to naturally investigate the performance of the unlearned global model. For backdoor attacks, we use a ‘pixel pattern’ trigger of size 3×3 using the Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (Nicolae et al., 2018), and change the label to ‘9’. When applying the backdoor attack, we exclude the data sample whose label is already the target label.

Results and Discussion: We consider two scenarios: (i) $N = 5$ clients with the target client having 66% of their images backdoored, and (ii) $N = 10$ clients with the target client having 80% of their images backdoored. Table 1 shows the clean and the backdoor accuracy on various models for these two cases. The ‘‘FedAvg’’ column reports the performance of the final global model (\mathbf{w}^T) learned as a result of federated learning. The ‘‘Retrain’’ column (the baseline approach) reports the clean and the backdoor accuracy when the model is retrained from scratch (without the participation of the target client). The ‘‘Reference Model’’ column reports the performance of the reference model (\mathbf{w}_{ref}), which is the average model for all but the target client. The ‘‘UN-Local Model’’ column reports the performance of the unlearned local model of the target client (\mathbf{w}_i^u). The ‘‘UN-Global Model’’ column shows the performance of the unlearned global model (after doing one round of FL training on the unlearned local model without the participation of the target client). We observe that the proposed PGD-based unlearning method successfully unlearns the contribution of the target client, achieving a low accuracy on the backdoored data (from 92.32% to 8.68% for $N = 10$) and a high accuracy on the rest of the data. We also observe that the proposed unlearning method achieves similar clean and backdoor accuracy to the baseline (i.e., retraining from scratch).

Let us focus on the second row of Table 1 (case (ii)) to discuss the results. The FL model \mathbf{w}^T (FedAvg column) has high clean as well backdoor accuracy, which indicates that it has properly learned both clean and backdoor data distributions. Our goal is to unlearn the backdoor data distribution from the model, and the target backdoor accuracy is around 10%, achieved by the baseline (Retrain column). The unlearning scheme relies on the reference model \mathbf{w}_{ref} (Reference column) which has learned the clean data distribution (indicated by its high clean accuracy), but also has some *memory* of the backdoor data distribution (indicated by its moderately high backdoor accuracy). After projected gradient ascent, the unlearned model \mathbf{w}_i^u (UN-Local column) effectively unlearns the backdoor data distribution (indicated by its 0% backdoor accuracy), without completely forgetting the clean data distribution (reflected by its decent clean accuracy). After doing one round of FL training starting with \mathbf{w}_i^u , we get the global unlearned model (UN-Global column) which recovers high clean accuracy.

To compare the speedup of the proposed method to the

Table 1. Accuracy results of various unlearning methods.

	FedAvg		Retrain		Reference Model		UN-Local Model		UN-Global Model	
N	Clean	Backdoor	Clean	Backdoor	Clean	Backdoor	Clean	Backdoor	Clean	Backdoor
5	98.13	89.5	98.38	10.03	98.15	81.14	15.46	0.0	94.09	9.98
10	98.78	92.32	97.26	9.91	98.8	89.53	46.01	0.0	94.33	8.68

baseline of retraining, we compute the clean and backdoor accuracy of both methods with respect to the number of FL training rounds after unlearning (as shown in Figure 1). For full retrain, we start FL training from a random model while for our method we start FL training on the unlearned local model without the participation of the target client (as discussed in Section 5). After one round of post-training, the proposed method reaches a clean accuracy of 93.64% and a backdoor accuracy of 7.87% for $N = 10$ (when there are 10 clients in the FL process). The baseline method requires more than 5 training rounds to achieve a similar performance. Overall, we observe that the proposed unlearning method is more efficient in terms of computation and communication cost on the retained clients than the baseline of retraining while achieving comparable clean and backdoor accuracy. We believe that lowering the computation and communication burden on retained clients is appealing in practice, since these clients are not incentivized to help the target client in unlearning.

Figure 1. Clean and backdoor accuracy of the proposed method and full retrain with respect to the number of rounds.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a novel federated unlearning method that can successfully unlearn the contribution of any client by reversing the learning process. Our method relies on the client that wants to opt out of federation without requiring the server (or any other client) to keep track of the history of their parameter updates. We have used the backdoor attacks to effectively evaluate the performance of the proposed method. Our empirical results have shown the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed unlearning method. As a future work, we will evaluate our method on different datasets and neural network architectures.

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References

- Act, P. Personal information protection and electronic documents act. *Department of Justice, Canada. Full text available at <http://laws.justice.gc.ca/en/P-8.6/text.html>*, 2000.
- Bagdasaryan, E., Veit, A., Hua, Y., Estrin, D., and Shmatikov, V. How to backdoor federated learning. In *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 2938–2948. PMLR, 2020.
- Baumhauer, T., Schöttle, P., and Zeppelzauer, M. Machine unlearning: Linear filtration for logit-based classifiers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.02730*, 2020.
- Bourtole, L., Chandrasekaran, V., Choquette-Choo, C. A., Jia, H., Travers, A., Zhang, B., Lie, D., and Papernot, N. Machine unlearning. In *2021 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, pp. 141–159. IEEE, 2021.
- Cao, Y. and Yang, J. Towards making systems forget with machine unlearning. In *2015 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, pp. 463–480. IEEE, 2015.
- Chen, M., Zhang, Z., Wang, T., Backes, M., Humbert, M., and Zhang, Y. When machine unlearning jeopardizes privacy. In Kim, Y., Kim, J., Vigna, G., and Shi, E. (eds.), *CCS ’21: 2021 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, Virtual Event, Republic of Korea, November 15 - 19, 2021*, pp. 896–911. ACM, 2021.
- Du, M., Chen, Z., Liu, C., Oak, R., and Song, D. Lifelong anomaly detection through unlearning. In *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pp. 1283–1297, 2019.
- Ginart, A., Guan, M., Valiant, G., and Zou, J. Y. Making ai forget you: Data deletion in machine learning. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 32, 2019.
- Golatkar, A., Achille, A., and Soatto, S. Eternal sunshine of the spotless net: Selective forgetting in deep networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 9304–9312, 2020a.

- Golatkar, A., Achille, A., and Soatto, S. Forgetting outside the box: Scrubbing deep networks of information accessible from input-output observations. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pp. 383–398. Springer, 2020b.
- Graves, L., Nagisetty, V., and Ganesh, V. Amnesiac machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.10981*, 2020.
- Gu, T., Dolan-Gavitt, B., and Garg, S. Badnets: Identifying vulnerabilities in the machine learning model supply chain. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.06733*, 2017.
- Guo, C., Goldstein, T., Hannun, A., and Van Der Maaten, L. Certified data removal from machine learning models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.03030*, 2019.
- Kairouz, P., McMahan, H. B., Avent, B., Bellet, A., Bennis, M., Bhagoji, A. N., Bonawitz, K., Charles, Z., Cormode, G., Cummings, R., D’Oliveira, R. G. L., Eichner, H., Rouayheb, S. E., Evans, D., Gardner, J., Garrett, Z., Gascón, A., Ghazi, B., Gibbons, P. B., Gruteser, M., Harchaoui, Z., He, C., He, L., Huo, Z., Hutchinson, B., Hsu, J., Jaggi, M., Javidi, T., Joshi, G., Khodak, M., Konečný, J., Korolova, A., Koushanfar, F., Koyejo, S., Lepoint, T., Liu, Y., Mittal, P., Mohri, M., Nock, R., Özgür, A., Pagh, R., Qi, H., Ramage, D., Raskar, R., Raykova, M., Song, D., Song, W., Stich, S. U., Sun, Z., Suresh, A. T., Tramèr, F., Vepakomma, P., Wang, J., Xiong, L., Xu, Z., Yang, Q., Yu, F. X., Yu, H., and Zhao, S. Advances and open problems in federated learning. *Foundations and Trends® in Machine Learning*, 14(1–2):1–210, 2021.
- Lecun, Y., Bottou, L., Bengio, Y., and Haffner, P. Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 86(11):2278–2324, 1998. doi: 10.1109/5.726791.
- Li, S., Xue, M., Zhao, B. Z. H., Zhu, H., and Zhang, X. Invisible backdoor attacks on deep neural networks via steganography and regularization. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 18(5):2088–2105, 2020.
- Liu, G., Ma, X., Yang, Y., Wang, C., and Liu, J. Federer: Enabling efficient client-level data removal from federated learning models. In *2021 IEEE/ACM 29th International Symposium on Quality of Service (IWQoS)*, pp. 1–10. IEEE, 2021.
- Liu, Y., Fan, M., Chen, C., Liu, X., Ma, Z., Wang, L., and Ma, J. Backdoor defense with machine unlearning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.09538*, 2022.
- McMahan, B., Moore, E., Ramage, D., Hampson, S., and y Arcas, B. A. Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data. In *Artificial intelligence and statistics*, pp. 1273–1282. PMLR, 2017.
- Melis, L., Song, C., De Cristofaro, E., and Shmatikov, V. Exploiting unintended feature leakage in collaborative learning. In *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, pp. 691–706. IEEE, 2019.
- Nasr, M., Shokri, R., and Houmansadr, A. Comprehensive privacy analysis of deep learning: Passive and active white-box inference attacks against centralized and federated learning. In *2019 IEEE symposium on security and privacy (SP)*, pp. 739–753. IEEE, 2019.
- Neel, S., Roth, A., and Sharifi-Malvajerdi, S. Descent-to-delete: Gradient-based methods for machine unlearning. In *Algorithmic Learning Theory*, pp. 931–962. PMLR, 2021.
- Nicolae, M.-I., Sinn, M., Tran, M. N., Buesser, B., Rawat, A., Wistuba, M., Zantedeschi, V., Baracaldo, N., Chen, B., Ludwig, H., Molloy, I., and Edwards, B. Adversarial robustness toolbox v1.2.0. *CoRR*, 1807.01069, 2018. URL <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.01069>.
- Pardau, S. L. The california consumer privacy act: Towards a european-style privacy regime in the united states. *J. Tech. L. & Pol’y*, 23:68, 2018.
- Sekharia, A., Acharya, J., Kamath, G., and Suresh, A. T. Remember what you want to forget: Algorithms for machine unlearning. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34, 2021.
- Thudi, A., Deza, G., Chandrasekaran, V., and Papernot, N. Unrolling sgd: Understanding factors influencing machine unlearning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.13398*, 2021.
- Voigt, P. and Von dem Bussche, A. The eu general data protection regulation (gdpr). *A Practical Guide, 1st Ed., Cham: Springer International Publishing*, 10(3152676): 10–5555, 2017.
- Wang, J., Guo, S., Xie, X., and Qi, H. Federated unlearning via class-discriminative pruning. In *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2022*, pp. 622–632, 2022.
- Wu, C., Zhu, S., and Mitra, P. Federated unlearning with knowledge distillation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.09441*, 2022.
- Wu, Y., Dobriban, E., and Davidson, S. B. Deltagrad: Rapid retraining of machine learning models. In *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML’20. JMLR.org*, 2020.
- Zhao, S., Ma, X., Zheng, X., Bailey, J., Chen, J., and Jiang, Y.-G. Clean-label backdoor attacks on video recognition models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 14443–14452, 2020.

A. Details on Hyperparameters

During FL training, we use the SGD optimizer with the following hyperparameters:

- Momentum $\beta = 0.9$
- Learning rate $\eta = 0.01$
- Batch size $B = 128$
- Number of epochs $E = 1$
- Aggregation algorithm: FedAvg (described in Section 3)

For PGD-based unlearning, we use the SGD optimizer with the following hyperparameters:

- Momentum $\beta = 0.9$
- Learning rate $\eta_u = 0.01$
- Batch size $B_u = 1024$
- Number of epochs $E_u = 5$
- ℓ_2 -norm ball radius δ is set to be one third of the average Euclidean distance between w_{ref} and a random model, where the average is computed over 10 random models
- Early stopping threshold $\tau = 12\%$
- Gradient ℓ_2 -clipping is employed with radius 5

For FL post-training after unlearning, we use the SGD optimizer with the following hyperparameters:

- Momentum $\beta = 0.9$
- Learning rate $\eta_u = 0.01$
- Batch size $B_u = 128$
- Number of SGD updates = 25 (We consider *computationally light rounds*, where each client only takes 25 mini-batch SGD updates as opposed to making a full pass over training data)
- Aggregation algorithm: FedAvg

Overview of the approach. Unlearning with projected gradient ascent is formulated as a constrained optimisation problem where given a trained model and the data to be removed, the algorithm obtains an updated model in the vicinity of the original model which exhibits poor performance on the deleted data. The neighborhood is modelled as an ℓ_2 -norm ball of radius δ around w_{ref} as shown in Fig. 2. In an FL setting, a natural choice of such a w_{ref} can be obtained by removing the appropriately scaled last update from the current global model. The algorithm proceeds by taking gradient steps in the direction that maximises the empirical loss (eq. 1) on its local data which is represented by the red arrows in Fig. 2. By constraining the parameters to remain within the feasible region of this optimisation problem, the algorithm ensures retention of performance with respect to other clients. The choice of ℓ_2 -norm ball for this feasible set is also consistent with the observations in (Thudi et al., 2021) which argue the use of Euclidean distance on model parameters for unlearning verification. The combined choice of δ and w_{ref} can be used to balance the performance trade-off between deleted and retained clients. As we noted in our experiments, even with a slight compromise in clean accuracy (retention) w_i^u quickly recovers after a few steps of re-training.

Figure 2. A schematic to illustrate the main idea of the proposed projected gradient ascent unlearning method (Algorithm 1).